

EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES FOR FIBER COMPOSITES WITH RHOMBIC PATTERN AND IMPERFECT INTERFACE

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1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced composites get an increasing attention in the development of new materials. By controlling the manufacturing process, it is possible to get the desired material properties. With the recent advances in numerical modeling of composites, it is possible to predict the effective material properties of the composites.

A number of numerical and analytical methods have been developed to estimate the effective coefficients using homogenization methods. By micro-mechanical models based on unit cell or representative volume element (RVE) the problem can be reduced on investigation of a periodic part of an infinite structure. But existing approaches are often restricted to certain types of arrangements. Mostly simple arrangements like square or hexagonal patterns have been investigated which result in an overall transverse isotropic behavior of the composite. An interesting goal is to create composites with orthotropic behavior in the transverse plane which can be achieved by rhombic fiber arrangements in connection with high volume fraction for the fibers [1].

Furthermore mostly the contact between matrix and fiber is considered as perfect. But in reality the connection between the phases is more or less weak, e.g. caused by certain fiber coatings. These coatings can be considered as a third phase. But this phase is typically very thin and numerical homogenization models based on finite element discretization fail when this intermediate phase becomes too thin.

A number of analytical approaches have been developed to consider the influence of the interface stiffness [2]-[5].

In this paper a numerical homogenization approach with finite elements (FE) is presented which includes imperfect interface conditions based on a

spring type model to overcome discretization problems of the intermediate phase [6]. This model is applied to fiber reinforced composites with rhombic fiber arrangements.

To validate the algorithm comparisons with three phase models and analytical solutions from literature are made. Finally studies are done to estimate the influence of the rhombic angle and the stiffness of the interface.

2 Model and algorithm

The numerical algorithm is based on a micro-mechanical unit cell model.

Fig. 1. Rhombic pattern and extracted unit cell

In Fig. 1 a periodic array with rhombic fiber distribution and the extraction of an appropriate unit cell are shown. The rhombic pattern is described by the global coordinate system x_1 - x_2 and the rhombic angle is α . Using a local coordinate system x_1' - x_2'

which is parallel to the rectangle edges (see Fig. 1) all calculations can be done similar to a square or hexagonal cell. But the final results are referred to the global axes by rotation around the angle $\alpha/2$.

To calculate all coefficients of the material tensor the used unit cell model is three dimensional with a certain depth in third direction (Fig. 2). The calculations were made with FE package ANSYS.

The interface between matrix and fiber can be modeled with a third solid phase (three phase model) or springs (see Fig. 2). In the three phase model there is a thin layer of solid elements (Fig. 2b) that means there is a distance between matrix and fiber. In case of springs there is no distance that means matrix and fiber nodes have the same coordinates at interface but double numbering for including the springs (Fig 2c).

Fig. 2. 3D FE unit cell (a) Solid interface (b) Spring interface (c)

In this paper the focus is set to the spring model but the three phase model is used for comparison.

The imperfect interface conditions are based on continuous stresses and discontinuous displacements. These two quantities are connected by a spring type in the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{rr}^m &= \sigma_{rr}^f = K_r \|u_r\| \\ \sigma_{r\theta}^m &= \sigma_{r\theta}^f = K_\theta \|u_\theta\| \\ \sigma_{rz}^m &= \sigma_{rz}^f = K_z \|u_z\| \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The values σ_{rr}^j , $\sigma_{r\theta}^j$ and σ_{rz}^j are the surface traction components with respect to a cylindrical coordinate system, which are related to either the fiber (f) or the matrix phase (m). The spring type parameters K_i , $i = r, \theta, z$ have the dimension of stresses divided by length. Double bar for the displacement quantities defines differences of displacements between matrix and fiber phase.

Hashin [3] defined the spring type parameters by derivation the imperfect contact formulation from a three phase problem with thin interphase thickness. If the interphase material is isotropic, they have the form

$$\begin{aligned} K_r &= \frac{E^i (1-\nu^i)}{t(1-2\nu^i)(1+\nu^i)}, \\ K_\theta &= \frac{G^i}{t}, \\ K_z &= \frac{G^i}{t}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where E^i , ν^i , G^i and t are Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, shear modulus and radial directional thickness of the interphase, respectively.

In the finite element model every nodal pair between fiber and matrix is connected by three springs in r , θ and z direction where the spring constants K_i^* are used from the relation

$$K_i^* = K_i A^s, \quad i = r, \theta, z. \quad (3)$$

A^s is the partial area of the whole area between matrix and fiber which belongs to the spring. Finally K_i^* has the typical string dimension force per length.

The homogenized effective material constants C_{ijkl}^{eff} can be derived from the constitutive relation

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = C_{ijkl}^{eff} \langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle \quad (4)$$

by

$$C_{ijkl}^{eff} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle}{\langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle}, \quad k = l, \quad (5)$$

$$C_{ijkl}^{eff} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle}{2\langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle}, \quad k \neq l.$$

Here $\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle$ and $\langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle$ are the averaged stresses and strains for the RVE which can be calculated for the three phase model from element quantities in the following manner

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = \frac{1}{V_{rve}} \sum_{e=1}^{ne} \sigma_{ij}^e V^e \quad (6)$$

$$\langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle = \frac{1}{V_{rve}} \sum_{e=1}^{ne} \varepsilon_{kl}^e V^e$$

σ_{ij}^e and ε_{kl}^e are averaged element stresses and strains, ne is the total number of elements and V_{rve} is the total RVE volume.

For the spring type model the averaged strains $\langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle$ include an additional term which represents the elasticity of the springs

$$\langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle = \frac{1}{V_{rve}} \sum_{e=1}^{ne} \varepsilon_{kl}^e V^e + \frac{1}{2V_{rve}} \sum_{s=1}^{ns} (\|u_k\| n_l + \|u_l\| n_k) A^s. \quad (7)$$

The values n_k and n_l are the k -th and l -th component of the outer normal vector, respectively, where the normal vector is related to the fiber phase. A^s is the partial area for a spring mentioned in eq. (3) and ns is the number of springs.

For averaged stresses there is no additional term because of the condition in eq. (1).

By applying three pure traction states and three pure shear states in such a manner that only one

component in the strain vector is non-zero all effective coefficients can be calculated with eq. (5). The six load cases can be produced by appropriate prescribed displacements and periodic boundary conditions which are ensured by constraint equations between nodal pairs of opposite surfaces of the RVE [1].

3 Results

3.1 Verification

In order to verify the correctness of the implemented algorithm a comparison with results reported by Hashin [3] is presented. In his paper he considers a transverse isotropic composite which is equivalent with hexagonal fiber arrangement. Furthermore with his model he calculated effective transverse bulk modulus and axial shear modulus.

To use our numerical algorithm for rhombic fiber arrangements the special case for a rhombic angle of 60° is chosen which is equivalent to a hexagonal cell. The volume fraction of the fiber is fixed to a value of 0.4. The material properties for the matrix and fiber phase are characterized by a constant ratio of the shear moduli (Hashin [3])

$$\frac{G^f}{G^m} = 10 \quad (8)$$

In addition to the shear ratio the Poisson's ratios of the matrix and fiber phase are 0.35 and 0.2, respectively. Since the imperfect contact condition is derived from a three phase problem, where the interphase has isotropic material behavior, the Poisson's ratio is defined by 0.3. The shear modulus is also predefined, but not fixed, since it shall be varied. The interphase thickness is given by the dimensionless parameter

$$\eta = \frac{t}{r^f} \quad (9)$$

For comparison according to Hashin [3] two values of η are chosen, 0.001 and 0.01.

In Figs. 3 and 4 the normalized effective transverse bulk modulus and the normalized effective axial shear modulus for $\eta=0.001$ are plotted. Normalization is done by relation between interphase shear modulus and matrix shear modulus

G^i/G^m . Beside the results from the proposed spring model the plots contain values from own developed three phase models. Hashin's approach is based on his three phase composite cylinder assemblage (CCA) model which coincides for this type of composite with the generalized self-consistent scheme (GSCS) [3].

The results for the transverse bulk modulus as well as the axial shear modulus show good agreement between all three methods for values $\log(G^i/G^m) < 2$. A very small value represents almost no interactions between fiber and matrix, which is equivalent to a model with voids.

Fig. 3. Normalized transversal bulk modulus for 0.4 fiber volume fraction and $\eta=0.001$

Fig. 4. Normalized axial shear modulus for 0.4 fiber volume fraction and $\eta=0.001$

For values higher than two only the three phase models are in good agreement. The reason for the differences of the curves for three phase model and spring model in this region lies in the averaging process for the three phase model according to eq. (6). The contribution of the high interphase stiffness results in higher overall stiffness. But this is not realistic. For a thin interface with a very high stiffness the behavior tends to perfect bonding. This must lead to constant effective properties which are identical with a two phase model with perfect contact.

Fig. 5. Normalized transversal bulk modulus for 0.4 fiber volume fraction and $\eta=0.01$

Fig. 6. Normalized axial shear modulus for 0.4 fiber volume fraction and $\eta=0.01$

In Figs. 5 and 6 the results for the effective transversal bulk modulus and the axial shear modulus are plotted for $\eta=0.01$. This means for the three phase model the thickness of the interphase is increased by the factor 10. The graphs for $\eta=0.001$ and $\eta=0.01$ show similar behavior. But the gradient region of the effective properties is shifted one decimal power of G^i/G^m . A thicker interface results in lower effective stiffness in this gradient region. For very low interface stiffness (tendency to debonding) and very high interface stiffness (tendency to perfect bonding) the interface thickness has nearly no influence.

3.2 Parametric studies

In the following a more realistic composite model with unidirectional fibers is considered. Here the fibers have transversely isotropic material properties and the matrix is isotropic. The considered materials are epoxy and graphite, taken from Hashin [7]. Detailed information is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Material phase properties.

Epoxy		Graphite					
E	ν	E_a	ν_a	E_t	ν_t	G_a	G_t
[GPa]		[GPa]		[GPa]		[GPa]	[GPa]
3.45	0.35	345	0.2	9.66	0.3	2.07	3.72

In Figs. 7-10 transversal effective coefficients for rhombic fiber arrangements are plotted. The angle, which characterizes the rhombic distribution, is 45° and 75° , respectively. The fiber volume fraction is 0.4. The interface contact parameters are characterized by eq. (2), where the thickness parameter t is given by the dimensionless parameter $\eta=0.001$. All values for the effective stiffness coefficients are referred to the global coordinate system x_1, x_2 and x_3 .

Figs. 7 and 8 show the principal diagonal coefficients C_{1111}^{eff} and C_{2222}^{eff} . Differences of the values can be observed for low and high imperfect contact parameters. For 75° the differences are smaller than for 45° . The reason is a more obvious anisotropy in case of 45° [1]. Further investigations have shown that the transversal anisotropy increases with reduction of rhombic angle. This is caused by the different distances between the fibers in x_1' and

x_2' direction (see Fig. 1) which become more significant for small rhombic angles.

Fig. 7. Normalized transversal coefficients for 0.4 fiber volume fraction and $\alpha=45^\circ$

Fig. 8. Normalized transversal coefficients for 0.4 fiber volume fraction and $\alpha=75^\circ$

In Fig. 9 the off-diagonal coefficients C_{1122}^{eff} and C_{2211}^{eff} for $\alpha=45^\circ$ and $\alpha=75^\circ$ are plotted. For both angles these effective components show coincidence, which confirms the correctness of the used procedure.

The transversal shear coefficient for 45° and 75° can be observed in Fig. 10. It can be seen, that in case of very low interphase moduli the coefficient for 75° is much lower than for 45° .

Fig. 9. Normalized transversal off-diagonal coefficients for 0.4 fiber volume fraction

Fig. 10. Normalized transversal shear coefficients for 0.4 fiber volume fraction

4 Conclusions

In this paper homogenized coefficients for unidirectional fiber reinforced composites with isotropic and transversal isotropic constituents are derived from a numerical method, where the micro structure of the composite is characterized by a rhombic fiber distribution and imperfect interface between fiber and matrix. For the realization the development of an appropriate model for a FE analysis in ANSYS is described.

In order to verify the present method, effective coefficients are compared to values derived from a CCA model by Hashin [3]. Also a FE analysis

considering a three phase geometry is studied as another comparison. There is a good agreement with the compared models for low interface stiffness especially for the thinner interface with $\eta=0.001$. Also the CCA model and the FE model with three constituents show in all figures of comparison almost coincidence.

Afterwards effective results with regard to the imperfect contact model are presented, where the fiber phase has transversely isotropic material properties and the fiber distribution is 45° and 75° . The presented results show the influence of the interface stiffness and the rhombic angles to the effective coefficients.

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